

Integrated Hands-Free Electronic Patient Care Report (ePCR) Charting (IHeC): Designing the Architecture

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Abstract

The nature of paramedic workloads typically results in incomplete or lack of patient care reports on patient handover to emergency department staff. Patient information gaps can increase emergency department staff's workload, cause care delays, and increase risks of adverse events. An integrated hands-free electronic patient care report (ePCR) could eliminate this gap. We conducted an environmental scan of the available literature on technologies to improve paramedic documentation and current advanced paramedic charting systems. Two technologies, speech recognition documentation and live telemetry sharing systems, were identified as potential improvements. A theoretical architecture for an integrated hands-free ePCR charting (IHeC) system was developed by combining these technologies. The ePCR could be completed and available upon patient arrival to the hospital using speech recognition and vital sign sharing technology. The IHeC system could solve the problem of patient information gaps and provide a platform for more advanced integration of paramedic services.

Introduction

During emergency response calls, paramedics must balance the need to provide immediate life-saving interventions and record clinical findings in a patient care report or an electronic patient care report (ePCR). Accurate recording of the ePCR is critical to safely hand off patients to emergency department (ED) staff. However, to focus on providing care, the ePCR is often completed and faxed to the ED after the patient handover¹. This is due to paramedic crews typically consisting of only two practitioners: the patient-responsible paramedic, who provides patient care, and the operation paramedic, who is responsible for the vehicle operation and support. Without the capacity to chart during patient care and transportation, paramedics are often forced to recall details after the patient is handed over to the ER staff and no longer under the care of the paramedics. This can lead to inaccurate charting².

An information gap occurs when information collected from paramedics is unavailable to the ER team. One study reported an information gap in 32% of patients delivered to the ED by paramedic crews¹. To address this gap, paramedics often provide a verbal handover, referring to a structured verbal report of the most critical patient information. This allows for the patient care report to be faxed to the ER department later in the day. Despite the potential benefits, verbal handovers have been reported to provide only 73-75% of details important to the patient's treatment^{3,4}. Mnemonic devices have been suggested to standardize and simplify verbal handovers. However, mnemonic devices are not reliably applied at the time of transfer⁵. Paramedics and ED staff often face competition for attention between providing care and engaging in a verbal handover, allowing for the opportunity for misunderstanding or misinterpretation. Also, delays in obtaining the ePCR can cause physician frustration, as 98% of physicians preferred to have the ePCR attached to the patient's electronic medical record (EMR) upon arrival at the hospital⁶.

To explore the issue of information gaps due to incomplete or missing ePCRs, an environmental scan was conducted to investigate two key areas. First, we identified current opportunities for technologies to improve efficiency and reduce the workload burden of healthcare providers that could be applied to paramedicine. Second, we explored opportunities to use currently deployed or in-development ePCR systems that have the potential to improve both workflow and charting accuracy through technology integration.

Methods

A broad search strategy was employed. Using an iterative process of searching key terms such as "speech recognition," "speech-to-text," "paramedicine," "paramedic," "pre-hospital technologies," "electronic patient care records," "EMS charting technologies," and "advanced prehospital charting" in four databases (MEDLINE, IEEE Explore, Google Scholar, and CINAHL), we reviewed current publications regarding ePCR documentation technologies. Search engines, like Google, were used to identify grey literature and industry websites. Finally, once articles were identified through the initial search, a review of the references within those articles was undertaken to identify any further publications that were missed in the initial search.

Results

Technologies to Ease Workload Burden

The search results revealed two technologies that could ease the workload burden and increase ePCR charting efficiency and accuracy. First, speech recognition (SR) technology in health has been well-studied over decades⁷. Zuchowski and Goller (2022) found that providers spent less time and made fewer errors when using SR documentation technology⁸. A controlled observational study of physicians by Blackley et al. (2020) found that SR decreases the time to complete medical documentation and creates more complete (longer) notes that are less error-prone⁹. In a direct comparison of SR entry to typed entry medical documentation for physicians, it was identified that there were fewer workflow interruptions when using SR entry¹⁰. Recent advancements in natural language processing (NLP), noise-reduction, speech synthesis, and pre-processing have made SR technologies more efficient and viable in a pre-hospital environment^{11, 12}. SR technologies have reduced physician workloads, decreased errors, and improved efficiency¹¹. These same benefits could be realized in paramedicine charting by implementing SR in ePCR documentation.

Second, live telemetry and sharing systems can automatically update an ePCR or transmit patient information directly to the intended destination (e.g., directly communicated with the hospital prior to arrival). The Operational Medical Networks Informatics Integrator (OMNII) system is an excellent example of this technology and has been actively deployed in Singapore since August 26, 2021¹³. The real-time transfer of patients' vital signs to receiving hospitals is a well-developed technology. The manufacturers of advanced monitoring devices, such as Phillips, Zoll, Physio-Control, and GE, all have integrated communication features in paramedics' devices. The manufacturers have developed their own sharing/viewing platforms based on cloud technology. These include RescueNet, LifeNet, IntelliSpace, and Muse^{14, 15}. Zoll has also developed a software development kit that allows for easy integration of their platform in other ePCRs and transmission systems¹⁴. A study from Japan found that using these types of vital sign-sharing systems significantly increased the number of precise vital signs received by the physician¹⁶.

IHeC Prototype Design

Combining SR documentation and telemetry and sharing systems into one system can increase charting efficiency and decrease patient information gaps. The proposed platform uses automated vital sign monitoring platforms, such as the physio-control LifePak 15 monitor and LifeNet systems¹⁵. This platform would integrate an ePCR with a limited-domain NLP SR input system. Using NLP in the SR entry would allow for fewer workflow interruptions and could be a natural extension of current practices used by paramedic services. Combining the two technologies, referred to as an Integrated Hands-Free ePCR Charting (IHeC), would allow immediate and accurate charting of vital signs and paramedic interventions. IHeC, outlined in Figure 1, would involve using a mobile device that would connect to an earpiece or hard-wired microphone and headset worn by the paramedic.

Figure 1. Framed concept outline of the Integrated Hands-Free ePCR Charting (IHeC) system.

This device would then use existing cellular networks to connect to a cloud service for NLP, which would identify and record the data into a local ePCR. The device could also use a wireless local area network (WLAN) to connect to a local system for processing. This could be located either in the ePCR device (laptop) or the ambulance itself in areas of poor cellular coverage. The interface would consist of command phrases that activate limited domains for NLP to detect the relevant information. For example, a paramedic could say, “Intervention, IV start, right hand, 18-gauge, TKO flow rate”. The system would recognize the command word, scan the following conversation, and identify pre-determined (closed domain) information for documentation. Once the program has the pre-determined information selected, it will use a form of closed-loop communication common in medical practice by repeating the recorded information back, or an alternative could be tactile feedback, like vibration, to let the paramedic know the required information was found and recorded. An example of how this could work can be found in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Intervention Command Set Examples

Paramedic: "Intervention. IV start, right hand, 18-gauge, successful attempt, TKO"

Intervention Type: (The intervention type determines the following fields)

IV Size (Line Gauge): Anatomic location: Initial Flow Rate: Successful Attempt:

IHeC: (Closed Loop) "IV 18 Gauge right-hand TKO"

Paramedic: "Intervention. Medication, IM EPI 1:1000, 1mg, Left shoulder. Expires Oct 24, Lot number 123456."

Intervention Type: (The intervention type determines the following fields)

Medication: Dose: Route: Anatomic location: Exp: Lot:

IHeC: (Closed Loop) "1mg EPI 1:1000 IM, Left Deltoid"

Figure 2. Example of IHeC Command Phrases set up using limited domain NLP implementation.

Figure 3. Command word entry structure for NLP processing.

The second arm of the IHeC solution would involve leveraging existing vital sign-sharing software. This would allow for the automatic recording of real-time vital signs using an advanced monitoring device (such as the Physio LifePak). The LifeNet version of the sharing software allows for sharing real-time cardiac monitoring and electrocardiogram recordings¹⁵. The software would record any interventions performed using the device, such as cardioversion, pacing, and defibrillation. Currently, paramedics must manually record these interventions and interpretations of the electrocardiograms separately in an ePCR. Similar to the OMNII system¹³, the IHeC system could automatically upload all timestamped interventions to the ePCR. IHeC would take vital signs at predetermined intervals and record them in the ePCR automatically. In a more advanced implementation, IHeC would stream real-time vital signs to the receiving hospital and any interventions the paramedic performs. Automating the recording of vital signs in an ePCR would enable paramedics to focus on direct patient care.

Adapting to paramedicine services integration

Paramedicine in Canada operates under a variety of service provision and funding models, ranging from government-funded public utility models to private enterprises¹⁷. Paramedics also work in conjunction with various health

authorities in their jurisdiction. Given the differences, we propose adaptations to the IHeC based on levels of paramedicine services integration within jurisdictions. For example, the IHeC could be implemented within Alberta's province-wide electronic record system. Whereas, in British Columbia, each health region has its own electronic records system, which would require the ePCR to communicate with several different systems. Complete integration of IHeC with multiple electronic record systems would be complex. IHeC could be adapted and scaled within different jurisdictions based on its integration level. However, there could be multiple benefits to a highly integrated paramedic system.

Clinical decision support tools for paramedics

Implementing the IHeC could be instrumental in realizing the benefits of a highly integrated paramedic service with clinical decision support for paramedics to reduce medication or protocol errors. Also, the IHeC can reduce ED wait times by delivering patients directly to surgical wards or diagnostic imaging centers. Clinical decision support has been shown to improve patient triage accuracy, diagnostic accuracy, and patient outcomes, reduce errors, and improve the overall quality of paramedic care^{19, 20}. Advanced notification and live telemetry would accelerate and enhance the use of alternate destination programs already implemented in some areas of Canada, like the Ambulance New Brunswick prehospital early warning system. These programs allow paramedics to reduce the burden on the ED by delivering the patient to a more appropriate destination, such as an urgent care center or addictions treatment, and in some cases treating the patient at home and referring them to community programs^{21, 22, 23}. An example of how IHeC could be used in a highly integrated system is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. IHeC as a highly integrated platform with clinical decision support and alternate destination models.

Discussion

Speech Recognition (SR) hands-free ePCR charting and telemetry and sharing systems for paramedics could address the missing or omitted patient information caused by delays in completing ePCR charting and verbal handovers. SR technology used by physicians in medical charting has been shown to reduce charting time, produce more complete notes, and is less error-prone than typed charting⁸. Recent advancements in SR charting technologies have made them viable for a noisy pre-hospital environment^{11, 12}. This advance, coupled with the already existing live telemetry capabilities of systems like OMNII in Singapore or the fully integrated AI/mixed reality ambulance introduced by Mediwave and 1990 Suwa Seriya in Sri Lanka²⁴, could improve the accuracy and function of ePCR charting.

In the seminal paper, "Principals to Guide the Future of Paramedicine," Tavares et al. (2022) identified advancing technologies, like artificial intelligence or NLP, as one of the six cross-cutting enabling factors to ensure the progression of paramedicine in Canada²⁵. These technologies could also be a gateway to future potential improvements. With recent AI advancements, there is strong potential for introducing a clinical decision support system to reduce medical errors. Zhang et al. (2022) have conducted a series of pilot tests of a SmartGlass charting system that enables live telemedicine with the receiving healthcare team and scanning medically relevant data, such

as medications²⁶. These technologies could accelerate alternate ways for paramedics to deliver patients to hospitals, such as direct-to-floor delivery, potentially bypassing the ED and elevating ED wait times. Over and above the issue addressed, it could also allow for live telemedicine with ED physicians in trauma cases en route to the hospital, where patients could be delivered directly to surgery, bypassing the ED completely. Further, the IHeC could allow the implementation of a clinical decision support system to aid paramedics in reducing medication or protocol errors. Despite the many benefits, we acknowledge numerous challenges that can arise when implementing a new health information technology system²⁷, as there are high reported failure rates of new HIT projects between 40-70%²⁸. Considering cost challenges, privacy concerns, end-user adoption concerns, and infrastructure disparities, further research is needed to explore patient data protection, user requirements and perceptions of technologies, and advancements in cellular infrastructure, which can accelerate the adoption and proliferation of these systems.

Conclusion

The issue of incomplete or unavailable ePCRs at patient handover resulting in information loss has many adverse effects. It leads to increased ED times, adverse events, and disruptions in care continuity. Our proposed IHeC system could ease the workload burden of paramedics and allow for a more complete and detailed ePCR to be available to ED physicians upon arrival. The IHeC system can potentially eliminate or reduce the information gaps and increase the quality of care provided. In a highly integrated health system, there are numerous benefits. The use of technology in healthcare is proliferating. Paramedicine stands to benefit significantly from its implementation. The proposed IHeC system could solve some current problems, such as the loss of patient information during handovers, while serving as a foundation for implementing more advanced systems.

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